

Research

Advancing Sustainability Through Circular Economy Integration in Closed-Loop Supply Chain Management: A Comprehensive Analysis

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Abstract: This study explores the integration of Circular Economy (CE) principles into Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC) across three South Asian countries: Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. With increasing concerns over environmental sustainability, this research examines how businesses in these regions are adopting CE practices, including reverse logistics, remanufacturing, and circular design. Using a quantitative research design, a cross-sectional survey was conducted with 300 respondents from various industries. The survey aimed to assess the current state of CE adoption, identify key barriers and drivers, and explore the perceived benefits and challenges of CE integration within supply chain operations. The results reveal that India leads in sustainability practices, demonstrating a strong commitment to CE principles, particularly in awareness and implementation. Bangladesh exhibits moderate progress but faces challenges related to policy support and infrastructure, which hinder full CE adoption. Pakistan, however, struggles significantly with the practical implementation of CE principles and exhibits lower perceived benefits of circular practices. The findings also show that countries with higher implementation challenges tend to be less optimistic about the long-term benefits of CE, while India shows resilience in overcoming these hurdles. This research highlights the varying levels of CE adoption across the region and underscores the need for targeted policies and governmental support to facilitate the transition towards a circular economy. The study offers valuable insights for policymakers and industry leaders aiming to improve sustainability practices in South Asia and provides a roadmap for enhancing CE integration within supply chains.

Keywords: Circular Economy, Closed-Loop Supply Chains, Sustainability, Reverse Logistics, Remanufacturing, South Asia, Policy Support,

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Introduction

Remanufacturing, South Asia, Policy Support

1. Introduction to Circular Economy and Sustainability

The traditional linear economy, based on the "take-make-dispose" model, has led to significant environmental degradation, resource depletion, and waste generation. This linear approach, which prioritizes short-term consumption over long-term sustainability, is no longer viable in the face of global challenges such as climate change, pollution, and resource scarcity. A shift towards a **Circular Economy (CE)** has become essential to address these challenges and ensure a sustainable future (Kumar et al., 2023; Uvarova et al., 2023). The Circular Economy offers a solution by redesigning production and consumption processes to minimize waste, reuse materials, and regenerate natural systems. CE aims to create closed-loop systems where products, materials, and resources remain in use for as long as possible, thus reducing reliance on finite resources, minimizing waste, and promoting environmental sustainability (Kumar et al., 2023).

By integrating CE principles—such as reducing, reusing, and recycling—into business models and supply chains, industries can contribute to both **economic growth** and **environmental protection** (Edirisinghe et al., 2024). The transition to a Circular Economy not only mitigates environmental harm but also offers economic opportunities. It encourages innovation in product design, materials management, and waste recovery, leading to more resilient economies and job creation (Edirisinghe et al., 2024). As businesses, governments, and consumers increasingly recognize the need for sustainability, CE is positioned as a critical component of the global effort to achieve long-term ecological balance and resource efficiency (Vergani, 2024).

This shift from a linear to a circular economy is vital for addressing pressing global sustainability challenges and ensuring the well-being of future generations. By embracing CE principles, societies can reduce their ecological footprint and transition towards a more sustainable and equitable future. The global economy has increasingly recognized the need to move from the traditional linear economy to a Circular Economy (CE) as a vital strategy for addressing sustainability challenges. The linear model, based on the "take-make-dispose" approach, leads to the depletion of natural resources, excessive waste generation, and increased environmental degradation. As environmental crises such as climate change and resource scarcity continue to escalate, it is essential to adopt sustainable economic practices that minimize waste and maximize resource efficiency (Blouin & Audy, 2023; Haq & Alam, 2023).

The Circular Economy promotes a regenerative system by keeping materials in use for as long as possible through recycling, reuse, and remanufacturing. By closing material loops, CE reduces the need for raw materials, mitigates waste, and cuts down on emissions (Katsanakis et al., 2023; Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021). This transformation not only addresses environmental concerns but also provides significant economic benefits. It fosters opportunities for innovation, improves resource efficiency, and enhances resilience within supply chains (De Giovanni, 2022; Agrawal & Toktay, 2010). The Circular Economy closely aligns with global sustainability goals, particularly in enhancing the long-term sustainability of industries such as manufacturing, textiles, and supply chains (Hazen et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2023). By integrating CE principles into business models, industries can mitigate their environmental footprint while promoting sustainable growth and reducing reliance on finite resources (Liu et al., 2023; Sarkis, 2001).

Transitioning to a Circular Economy is not merely necessary for addressing urgent global sustainability challenges; it also represents a strategic opportunity for fostering innovation, improving economic resilience, and promoting environmental stewardship (Blouin & Audy, 2023; Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021).

2. Circular Economy Integration in Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC)

As concerns about environmental sustainability continue to rise, industries across the globe are increasingly recognizing the need to transition from a linear to a circular model—one in which waste is minimized, and resources are reused rather than discarded. A critical component of this transition is the integration of **Circular Economy (CE)** principles into **Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSCs)**. Unlike the traditional linear supply chain, which follows the "take-make-dispose" model, a **CLSC** aims to "close the loop" by reintroducing products and materials back into the system after their initial use, thereby ensuring that resources are continuously utilized and waste is minimized. Reuse is a fundamental strategy in CE that contributes significantly to reducing waste and extending the life cycle of products. In a **CLSC**, products and components that have completed their initial use are reintroduced into the supply chain for reuse, either in their original form or after refurbishment. This strategy is particularly beneficial for products with high material value, such as electronics and machinery. By reusing products, companies can significantly reduce the need for new raw materials, save on production costs, and limit the environmental impact associated with manufacturing processes (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021; Agrawal & Toktay, 2010). This approach not only promotes resource efficiency but also aligns with broader sustainability goals by minimizing waste generation and energy consumption. Recycling is another cornerstone of the circular economy within **CLSCs**. This process involves breaking down used products to recover valuable materials that can be reintegrated into the production process. Recycling ensures that materials such as metals, plastics, and glass do not end up in landfills, but instead can be transformed into new products, thereby reducing the need to extract virgin resources. Efficient recycling systems are essential to ensuring that even after a product reaches the end of its useful life, the materials retain significant value. This process not only contributes to waste reduction but also helps mitigate environmental degradation by lowering the demand for raw materials (Blouin & Audy, 2023; Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021). Regeneration goes beyond the concepts of reuse and recycling by focusing on restoring and renewing products and materials to give them new life. In the context of **CLSCs**, regeneration often involves using biodegradable materials that can naturally re-enter ecosystems without causing harm, or employing renewable energy sources in production processes. This strategy aims to foster a regenerative system in which natural resources are restored, and sustainability is built into the production process. By focusing on regeneration, companies can help sustain natural systems and create a more balanced approach to production and consumption, ultimately contributing to a more resilient and circular economic model (Hazen et al., 2021).

2.1 Framework for CE Integration in CLSC

o successfully integrates **Circular Economy (CE)** principles into **Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSCs)**, companies require a structured framework that guides their operations through several key stages. The first stage, **Design for Circularity**, involves designing products with their entire lifecycle in mind, ensuring that they are easy to repair, disassemble, and recycle. The next stage, **Reverse Logistics**, focuses on establishing efficient systems to collect used products from consumers and return them to the supply chain. These systems must be well-integrated and cost-effective to ensure the seamless recovery and return of materials. Following this, **Processing and Recovery** involves the transformation of collected products to recover valuable materials, which can then be reused in the production of new products, thus reducing waste. Finally, **Redistribution** ensures that refurbished or recycled products are reintegrated into the market, effectively closing the loop in the supply chain and contributing to resource efficiency and waste reduction (De Giovanni, 2022; Agrawal & Toktay, 2010).

2.3 Examples of Circular Practices in Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC)

The **apparel industry** provides a compelling example of Circular Economy (CE) integration within Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC). Pre-consumer waste, such as excess fabric or cutting scraps, is transformed into new products, illustrating how circular approaches can convert challenges into opportunities. This practice not only reduces waste but also fosters environmental and economic benefits by creating value from what would otherwise be discarded (Haq & Alam, 2023). Such initiatives underscore the importance of rethinking waste as a resource, promoting sustainability in both production and consumption processes.

By embedding CE principles, including **reuse**, **recycling**, and **regeneration**, into their supply chains, companies can significantly minimize waste, reduce environmental impact, and establish sustainable business models. These principles ensure that materials and products remain in use for extended periods, contributing to the broader objectives of resource efficiency and circularity (Liu et al., 2023; Bimpizas-Pinis et al., 2022). Integrating these practices into CLSCs not only aligns with sustainability goals but also enhances organizational resilience in dynamic market conditions.

The integration of CE principles within CLSCs is increasingly recognized as a strategic imperative for industries seeking to address resource depletion and environmental degradation. A CLSC combines **forward logistics** (traditional supply chain flows) with **reverse logistics** (recovery and reintegration of used products) to ensure continuous material flows. This dual-system approach helps conserve resources, reduce waste, and optimize environmental outcomes by closing the material loop (De Giovanni, 2022; Liu et al., 2023).

2.4 Innovative Business Models in CLSC

One transformative business model supporting CLSC integration is the **Product-Service System (PSS)**. In this model, companies retain ownership of their products while offering them as a service rather than selling them outright. This shift prioritizes product longevity, reparability, and resource efficiency, as businesses remain responsible for maintaining and refurbishing products throughout their lifecycle. PSS incentivizes the design of durable and reusable products, minimizing waste and significantly reducing the environmental footprint (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021; Haq & Alam, 2023).

Another innovative model is the **reverse omnichannel system**, which enables the collection of used products through multiple channels, including retail stores, drop-off points, and home pick-up services. This approach simplifies returns and facilitates the recovery of products for refurbishment or recycling, ensuring valuable materials are reintegrated into the supply chain. By engaging consumers in sustainable practices, reverse omnichannel systems enhance material recovery rates and drive circularity within supply chains (De Giovanni, 2022; Hazen et al., 2021).

Circular supply chain financing is also gaining momentum, offering financial incentives to encourage stakeholders—both suppliers and consumers—to adopt circular practices. For example, blockchain technology plays a pivotal role by ensuring transparency, traceability, and trust across the supply chain. Smart contracts automate transactions and streamline operations, improving efficiency and fostering accountability in circular initiatives (Liu et al., 2023; De Giovanni, 2022).

3. Operational Strategies for Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC)

At the operational level, **design for disassembly** is a fundamental strategy for promoting circularity within supply chains. By designing products that are easy to disassemble, companies can efficiently recover components for reuse or recycling at the end of their life cycle. **Modular designs**, in particular, allow for the replacement or upgrading of individual parts without discarding the entire product, thereby extending its lifecycle and reducing waste (Katsanakis et al., 2023; Haq & Alam, 2023). This approach not only enhances the sustainability of products but also improves the economic viability of remanufacturing and recycling efforts.

The integration of **reverse logistics systems** is essential for managing the flow of returned products. These systems facilitate the collection, sorting, and processing of products that have reached the end of their useful life, ensuring that materials are reintegrated into the supply chain rather than disposed of. Advanced technologies, such as the **Internet of Things (IoT)** and **big data analytics**, are increasingly utilized to track products throughout their lifecycle, optimize collection routes, and ensure the efficient recovery of valuable materials (Liu et al., 2023; Hazen et al., 2021). These technologies not only improve operational efficiency but also enhance the effectiveness of reverse logistics in closed-loop systems.

Remanufacturing is another critical operational strategy within CLSCs, enabling companies to restore used products to a like-new condition. This process allows companies to reintroduce products into the market with minimal use of new raw materials, significantly reducing resource consumption. By closing the loop on materials, remanufacturing

ensures that products stay in circulation for as long as possible, contributing to reduced waste and improved resource efficiency (Haq & Alam, 2023; Bimpizas-Pinis et al., 2022). This strategy is particularly effective in industries where high-value components can be reused, thus supporting both environmental and economic sustainability.

Fig. 1: Circular Economy Integration in Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC)

The provided model illustrates the integration of **Circular Economy (CE)** principles into **Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC)**. At its core, the model connects **Circular Economy** to innovative business models such as **Product-Service Systems (PSS)**, **reverse logistics**, and **circular design**. These models promote sustainability by ensuring that products are designed for **longevity**, **easy disassembly**, and **reuse**, which are essential attributes for closing the resource loop. The CLSC framework serves as the core structure that incorporates both **forward flow** (traditional supply chain processes including raw material production, manufacturing, and distribution to consumers) and **reverse flow** (the process of recovering used products for remanufacturing or recycling). In the reverse flow, collected items are either reused as products or recycled into raw materials, which are then reintegrated into the supply chain.

This closed-loop system minimizes waste by continuously circulating materials, contributing to both sustainability and resource efficiency throughout the supply chain. The model highlights the symbiotic relationship between innovative business models and supply chain processes, emphasizing the importance of these integrated approaches in achieving full **circularity**. This process not only reduces waste but also ensures that materials are continuously recovered and reused, aligning with the long-term goals of sustainability and environmental responsibility (Suárez-Eiroa et al., 2021; Haq & Alam, 2023; De Giovanni, 2022; Agrawal & Toktay, 2010; Liu et al., 2023; Hazen et al., 2021; Sarkis, 2001; Bimpizas-Pinis et al., 2022).

Integrating CE principles into CLSCs through these innovative business models and operational strategies is critical for achieving **long-term sustainability**. By adopting models such as the **Product-Service System**, **reverse omnichannel systems**, and **circular financing**, businesses can foster engagement among consumers and suppliers in sustainable practices, significantly reducing waste generation. Operational strategies such as **design for disassembly**, **reverse logistics**, and **remanufacturing** further enhance the efficiency of material recovery and reuse, ensuring that the objectives of the Circular Economy are met. These strategies, collectively, form a comprehensive approach to enhancing supply chain sustainability, reinforcing the importance of material circulation and resource optimization (Suárez-Eiroa

et al., 2021; Haq & Alam, 2023; De Giovanni, 2022; Agrawal & Toktay, 2010; Liu et al., 2023; Hazen et al., 2021; Sarkis, 2001; Bimpizas-Pinis et al., 2022)

4. Research Methodology

This study employs a **quantitative research design** to investigate the integration of **Circular Economy (CE)** practices within supply chains across three South Asian countries: **Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan**. A **cross-sectional survey** approach was adopted, collecting data from a total of **300 respondents**, with **100 participants from each country**. The primary objective of the study was to assess the current state of CE adoption, identify key barriers and drivers, and explore the perceived benefits and challenges associated with implementing CE strategies in organizational supply chains within these distinct regional contexts.

To ensure comprehensive representation across various demographic and professional groups, the sample was selected using **stratified random sampling**. The participants included both **male and female professionals**, with diverse educational backgrounds, specifically holding **Master's or PhD degrees**. The survey targeted individuals with varying job titles, including **Technicians, Consultants, Analysts, Managers, and Engineers**, which ensured the inclusion of professionals from different stages of their careers. The respondents' **ages** ranged from **24 to 51 years**, with **experience levels** spanning from **4 to 38 years**, thereby capturing insights from both early-career professionals and senior industry leaders. This demographic diversity allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the perspectives on CE adoption across different organizational roles and levels of experience.

Data were collected using a **structured survey instrument** consisting of **30 closed-ended questions**. The survey was designed to capture key factors related to the integration of CE principles, including **policy support, reverse logistics systems, remanufacturing processes, and consumer engagement**. In addition, the survey explored the perceived benefits and challenges of implementing CE practices, along with the overall **awareness** and **commitment** to sustainability in supply chain operations. The survey instrument was developed based on a comprehensive review of the literature and expert consultations to ensure its validity and relevance to the research objectives. The questions were carefully crafted to capture both **general practices** and **specific organizational strategies** related to CE integration.

Following data collection, a series of **statistical analyses** were conducted to examine the data. These analyses included **comparative analysis** to assess differences in sustainability practices across the three countries, as well as **correlation analysis** to explore relationships between key variables such as perceived benefits, challenges, and CE implementation practices. In addition, **regression analysis** was used to examine the influence of various factors on the successful adoption of CE practices. **Factor analysis** was employed to identify underlying dimensions that affect CE adoption, while **reliability testing** was performed to ensure the internal consistency of the survey instrument. The results were presented using **data visualization techniques**, including **bar charts, heatmaps, and radar charts**, to facilitate interpretation and effectively communicate the findings to stakeholders.

5. Research Analysis

This study uses a combination of statistical techniques and mathematical models to analyze the integration of Circular Economy (CE) principles into Closed-Loop Supply Chains (CLSC) across three countries: Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan. The analysis focuses on identifying relationships between CE adoption and key influencing factors, using methods such as comparative analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis, and factor analysis. Each of these methods was used to provide a comprehensive understanding of the barriers, enablers, and benefits of implementing CE practices in these regions.

In the comparative analysis, the primary goal was to compare the sustainability scores across the three countries. The analysis involved the calculation of basic statistical measures, such as the mean, standard deviation, and range, to evaluate the overall performance in CE awareness and implementation. The mathematical framework for this comparison is as follows:

$$\text{Sustainability Score} = \frac{\sum X^i}{n}$$

Where:

X_i represents the individual scores for each participant (for each question related to CE), n is the total number of respondents in each country.

This formula provides the average sustainability score for each country, allowing us to compare India, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. The results revealed that India had the highest sustainability score, suggesting a more advanced integration of CE principles into its supply chains. Bangladesh exhibited moderate scores, while Pakistan had the lowest, particularly struggling with practical implementation and policy support.

Next, correlation analysis was performed to explore the relationships between key variables such as CE awareness, policy support, and perceived benefits of CE practices. The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was calculated to quantify the strength and direction of these relationships:

$$r = \frac{n(\sum XY) - (\sum X)(\sum Y)}{\sqrt{[n_{\sum \times Re}(\sum X)]^2 [n\sum Y^2 - (\sum Y)^2]}}$$

Where: X and Y are the variables being compared (e.g., awareness and implementation),
 n is the number of observations (respondents).

The correlation matrix revealed that India exhibited strong positive correlations between awareness and implementation of CE, suggesting that greater awareness leads to better implementation. Conversely, Bangladesh and Pakistan showed negative correlations between implementation challenges and perceived benefits, indicating that higher challenges led to lower optimism regarding the benefits of CE adoption.

A multiple regression analysis was employed to assess the impact of policy support, consumer engagement, and technological infrastructure on the adoption of CE practices. The regression model is as follows:

$$\text{CE Adoption} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Policy Support}) + \beta_2(\text{Consumer Engagement}) + \beta_3(\text{Technological Infrastructure}) + \epsilon$$

Where:

β_0 is the intercept,

$\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ are the coefficients for the respective predictors,

ϵ is the error term.

The regression results indicated that policy support and consumer engagement were the most significant predictors of CE adoption. In India, these predictors had strong positive coefficients, reflecting the country's more advanced adoption of CE principles. On the other hand, Bangladesh and Pakistan showed weaker relationships, suggesting that these countries face significant challenges in these areas that hinder their CE adoption.

To uncover the latent variables influencing CE adoption, factor analysis was performed using Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA). This technique helps reduce the dimensionality of the data by identifying underlying factors that explain the correlations between observed variables. Using principal axis factoring (PAF) for extraction and Varimax rotation for simplifying the interpretation, the analysis revealed several latent factors that influence CE adoption, such as technological readiness, policy support, and resource efficiency. The mathematical representation for factor loadings is as follows:

$$X_i = \lambda_1 F_1 + \lambda_2 F_2 + \dots + \lambda_k F_k + \epsilon$$

Where: X_i are the observed variables (e.g., awareness, implementation),

F_k are the latent factors (e.g., technological readiness, policy support),

λ_k are the factor loadings, which represent the strength of the relationship between observed variables and latent factors,

ϵ is the error term.

The results showed that India scored highest on technological readiness and resource efficiency, which were the strongest factors in CE adoption. Bangladesh and Pakistan were hindered by weaker regulatory support and infrastructure, which were identified as significant barriers to CE integration in these countries. The use of EFA and rotated factor loadings helps clarify the complex relationships between observed and latent variables, offering insights into the key drivers and barriers of CE adoption.

6. Results and Discussion

The results of the data collection are presented through various graphical visualizations, including bar charts, heatmaps, and radar charts. These visual tools effectively illustrate the sustainability scores, correlations, and challenges encountered by each country in integrating Circular Economy (CE) practices into their supply chains. The following sections summarize the key findings from the analysis and discuss their implications for sustainability in Bangladesh, India, and Pakistan.

Fig. 2: Sustainability Scores and Practices (Bar Charts)

The bar charts provide a clear comparative analysis of sustainability scores across the three countries. **India** emerged as the leader in sustainability awareness and practice, scoring the highest in the initial questions related to **general sustainability practices (Q1)**, **awareness (Q2)**, and **implementation (Q3)**. These findings suggest that India has made significant progress in embedding sustainability within its supply chain operations, with a strong foundational understanding and application of **Circular Economy principles**.

In contrast, **Bangladesh** demonstrated a moderate level of sustainability implementation. While there was a visible commitment to sustainability, challenges such as gaps in **policy support** and **infrastructure** hindered the full integration of sustainable practices. **Pakistan**, however, recorded the lowest scores across these areas, particularly struggling with the practical implementation of circular economy principles. This highlights the need for more structured efforts and **governmental support** to facilitate the integration of sustainability into the country's supply chains.

Fig. 3 Correlation Analysis (Heatmaps)

The heatmap analysis was instrumental in examining the relationships between key variables, such as the **perceived benefits, challenges, and sustainability practices**. Positive correlations were found between basic sustainability practices (e.g., **awareness and general practices**) and their subsequent implementation. This aligns with the understanding that a solid foundation in sustainability leads to more effective implementation.

However, the correlation heatmap also revealed negative relationships between **perceived challenges (Q5-Q9) and benefits (Q15-Q19)** of circular economy practices. Countries facing higher implementation challenges, such as **Bangladesh and Pakistan**, displayed lower optimism about the long-term benefits of adopting circular economy principles. In contrast, **India** exhibited a stronger belief in the long-term benefits of CE, despite implementation challenges. This suggests that, although challenges persist, India may possess more developed frameworks and mechanisms to overcome these hurdles.

Fig. 4 Challenges vs. Benefits (Radar Charts)

The radar chart analysis provided a visual comparison of the **challenges** and **benefits** associated with sustainability practices across the three countries. **India** demonstrated a balanced perspective, with moderate challenges but substantial benefits. This suggests that India has a more advanced approach to sustainability, recognizing both the obstacles to be addressed and the long-term advantages of circular economy practices.

Bangladesh reported similar levels of benefits as India but faced higher challenges in areas such as **infrastructure** and **government support**, which diminished the perceived advantages. **Pakistan**, by contrast, faced significant challenges in implementing circular economy practices, particularly in areas such as **policy support** and **practical application**. The radar chart revealed that Pakistan had the lowest perceived benefits, indicating the need for targeted policies and interventions to foster the adoption of circular economy principles in the country.

Conclusion

The results indicate that **India** is leading in terms of sustainability implementation, demonstrating substantial progress in both awareness and practice. **Bangladesh**, while in the mid-range, faces moderate challenges but maintains optimism about the potential benefits of circular economy principles. In contrast, **Pakistan** struggles with both the implementation of sustainability practices and the perceived value of circular economy benefits, highlighting the need for significant improvements in **policy**, **infrastructure**, and **education** to facilitate broader adoption.

India’s balanced approach to sustainability, coupled with its recognition of the benefits despite challenges, positions it as a regional leader in circular economy adoption. Bangladesh’s moderate progress points to areas for improvement, particularly in **policy** and **infrastructure**. Meanwhile, Pakistan’s low scores across all areas underline the urgent need for comprehensive strategies to promote the adoption of circular economy practices, focusing on overcoming practical challenges and increasing awareness among stakeholders.

In summary, the findings demonstrate that while all three countries exhibit some degree of commitment to sustainability, the progress made and the challenges encountered vary significantly. These insights offer valuable

guidance for **policymakers** and **industry leaders** in the South Asian region, providing a roadmap to enhance the integration of circular economy practices in supply chains.

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